

PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSIVENESS OF RURAL HEALTH UNITS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN CABANATUAN CITY

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Abstract

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has severely affected the delivery of health services in primary health care due to the fear and mistrust of healthcare. This study sought to determine how prepared the public primary health facilities are, particularly the RHUs, to mitigate virus transmission and how responsive they are to the non-health needs of the community people.

Methods: The study utilized descriptive-correlational research and a total population sampling of all healthcare providers working in the Rural Health Units in Cabanatuan City. The RHUs was found “better prepared” to identify, stop, and prevent epidemics based on the Ready Score Criteria. Additionally, the respondents were always responsive to the eight domains of health systems responsiveness.

Results: Correlation results found: (1) no significant relationship between the number of staff and the preparedness of the rural health unit; (2) positive correlation between the total number of staff and autonomy; (3) negative correlation between the total number of staff and choice of healthcare providers; (4) negative correlation between health facility readiness and prompt attention; and (5) negative correlation between health facility readiness and adequate quality of basic amenities.

Conclusions: Primary health care has played a significant role in promoting health and preventing disease transmission. Thus, improving the health system performance by being prepared in times of health crises safeguards the welfare of the people. A Comprehensive Health Enhancement Program for Rural Health Units is proposed. Further research on health system responsiveness is also recommended.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Preparedness, Primary Healthcare, Responsiveness, Enhancement Program

Introduction

Since its declaration as a pandemic in March 2020, the 2019 COVID-19 pandemic has affected global health systems. Mistrust of healthcare and financial restrictions during lockdowns cause 53% of health service disruptions in primary care. 92% of countries reported a deterioration in health care delivery (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Healthcare workers are also at high risk of COVID-19 infection and seven times more susceptible to severe illness (Nguyen et al., 2020). Infection prevention and control are crucial to protecting patients, healthcare workers, and health services due to its contagiousness. Health facilities must be virus-ready now. This research is scarce, especially in the Philippines.

The poorest Filipinos choose outpatient care at public primary care institutions (Dayrit, 2018). These facilities provide medical consultations, prenatal and postnatal checks, immunization, dental care, childbirth, and family planning. These facilities support their communities despite the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrating the importance of primary health care in disease epidemics. Due to increased patient numbers and poor infrastructure, commercial and public health facilities have struggled to comply with infection prevention and control procedures. Lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) has made the problem worse, endangering patients and healthcare workers. The pandemic tested health systems' ability to deliver universal health care goals like enhanced health, responsive systems, and equal health finance.

Pandemic, epidemic, and endemic are terminologies used when an outbreak of a particular disease happens at a specific locality or different places. A disease outbreak occurs when the number of disease cases exceeds the average expectancy (WHO, 2021). A pandemic, also known as a worldwide epidemic, is an outbreak of infectious illness that spreads rapidly across a large geographic region and has a high incidence, often affecting a major proportion of the global population for several months (Rogers, 2020). As it emerges unpredictably, disease outbreaks put the people and the healthcare system at enormous risks – like the case of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Health crises impact the health system, so preparation is essential. When there is no direct contact with the threat, all efforts are focused on forecasting, planning, and implementing solutions (Stoichitoiu & Baicus, 2021). Since most disaster-affected communities rely on primary healthcare facilities, Yari et al. (2021) state that unprepared healthcare institutions hinder service continuity. Kuy et al. (2020) also underlined the necessity of intervening early to avoid disruptions in health care delivery and guarantee that the health system continues to offer crucial treatment to the population, confirming that disaster health management choices affect pandemic outcomes (Plagg, 2021).

COVID-19 pandemics affect rural and urban areas. Kaufman (2020) states that almost half of rural residents are at danger of COVID-19 hospitalization and mortality. Rural areas have a significant risk of COVID-19 transmission (Arisanti et al., 2020; Peters, 2020), and many patients in many nations first contact primary care (Rawaf et al., 2020). Peters (2020) recommends reexamining each state's rural pandemic readiness plans to establish clear lines of power across jurisdictions, designate primary regional hospitals, store medical supplies, and manage health professional shortages. During an outbreak, a well-organized health system can provide equitable access to high-quality crucial health care, decreasing direct and indirect mortality (WHO, 2020).

Even with a pandemic preparedness strategy in place, governments are confronted with difficulties due to today's unprecedented event. Van Hoang et al. (2021) concluded that the Hanoi health system's readiness response in Vietnam was satisfactory despite capacity and resource restrictions. Seventy-four percent of Africa's countries have a pandemic preparedness strategy, but the majority are out of date; they lack the resources necessary to track down confirmed cases' direct contacts and establish quarantine facilities at airports and hospitals for suspected cases (Gilbert et al., 2020). Kanu et al. (2021) then found that healthcare personnel in Sierra Leone perceived their facility as unprepared for the COVID-19 pandemic, validating Parmley et al.'s (2021) conclusion that COVID-19 readiness is lacking.

Bayani and Tan studied COVID-19's effects on Philippine health systems (2021). NPIs and COVID-19 fear have changed healthcare practitioners' and patients' care-seeking habits. Emergent and non-emergent patients requiring expert treatment, especially those with complex pregnancies, stroke, or myocardial infarction, are most affected by community quarantine. Due to travel restrictions, several emergency case patients died in transit to secondary and tertiary facilities, while COVID-19 patients were rejected by nearby emergency rooms. However, several rural health units had more outpatient visits than usual pre-COVID, as patients chose a small facility over a hospital with a higher infection risk. Numerous towns have implemented telemedicine via hotlines or radio consultations. COVID-19 updates are shared via social media.

Research Questions

This study examined Cabanatuan City's Rural Health Units' COVID-19 preparedness and response. It specifically addressed these questions: (1) What is the profile of Rural Health Units in terms of total number of staff (including physicians, nurses, DOH Human Resource for Health, midwives, and other personnel), total number of covered barangays, average monthly outpatient visits before and during the pandemic, and total number of covered barangays? (2) What is their work title, age, sex, and civil status? (3) How prepared are Rural Health Units in terms of health facility, staff, risk communication, and supply readiness? (4) How responsive is the health system to respect for dignity, autonomy, privacy, confidentiality, rapid attention, appropriate quality of basic amenities, access to social support, choice of health care providers, and effective communication? (5) Does RHU profile, preparation, and health systems responsiveness have a substantial relationship?

Methodology

Research Design. This study used quantitative research to collect numerical data and statistically analyze it to answer questions or test hypotheses (Nieswiadomy & Bailey, 2018). Descriptive correlational (or simple correlational design) was used to describe and explain relationships without inferring causality (Polit & Beck, 2017; Gray et al., 2016).

Sampling Procedures. Total enumeration or total population sampling was used to pick this study's respondents. This sampling approach is suitable for small populations with a well-defined feature that eliminates bias.

Instrumentation. Since quantitative research often uses questionnaires, the study used one. Google Forms and research-assisted printing distributed the research instrument. Three sections—profile, preparation, and responsiveness—contained 63 items and two

altered standardized measures. So, a Nueva Ecija Rural Health Unit pilot test with 17 respondents passed the reliability test with 0.966 and 0.980, respectively.

Data Analysis. Tables and figures presented descriptive and inferential statistics-analyzed data. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to explain the RHU and respondents' profiles. Pearson Product-Moment RHU profile, preparedness, and responsiveness associations were examined using correlation.

Results

Profile of RHUs. Before the epidemic, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija's largest city, had 8480 monthly RHU visits. Pandemic outpatient visits dropped to 7356 per month, affecting primary care. In-person consultations dropped as non-communicable disease patients worried about getting the virus.

Profile of Respondents. The study surveyed City Health Center nurses, midwives, and doctors. Most responses (49) were nurses, followed by midwives (26) and doctors (8). The most respondents were 31-36 (31.33%), followed by 55-60 (3.61%) and 61+ (3.61%). Women outnumbered men (79.52% to 20.48%). Most nurses and midwives worldwide are women, who are more susceptible to infection (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2020).

Preparedness of Rural Health Units. Table 3.5 shows RHU readiness for COVID-19 entrance screening and triage. 85.90% of facilities screened and triaged. However, single rooms with doors for COVID-19 physical evaluation (84.34%), dedicated patient bathrooms in the waiting area (55.42%), and effective hand hygiene stations (7.23%) rated low. Several RHUs lack pandemic-critical infection prevention and control facilities. Hand hygiene stations and patient restrooms fared poorly during COVID-19 (Ashinyo et al., 2021; Hirai et al., 2021).

Table 1. Preparedness of Rural Health Units

Preparedness of Rural Health Units	Frequency of "Yes" answers	Percentage	Interpretation
1. Health Facility Readiness	926	94.90	Better Prepared
2. Health Staff Readiness	498		
3. Risk Communication	735		
4. Availability of Supplies	913		
Total (n=3237)	3072		

***Criteria:** The ReadyScore Criteria for Preparedness

80% or higher	Better Prepared
40 – 79%	Work to Do
39% or lower	Not Ready

In Table 1, Cabanatuan City RHUs scored 94.90 percent, indicating superior epidemic detection, prevention, and control. Most screening and triage departments lack patient bathrooms in the waiting area and solitary rooms for symptomatic patient physical evaluation. This study showed early epidemic countries need better health institutions. Ethiopian hospitals reported 52% needed improvement (Tolu et al., 2020). 26.1% of South Wollo health facilities were pandemic-ready, while the remainder needed "improvement"

(Ayele et al., 2021). Two of Uganda's seventeen referral institutes were ready; others needed development (Mwine et al., 2022). Chanie et al. (2021) found COVID-19-unprepared frontline staff. Yari et al. suggest majority use basic healthcare (2021). Peters (2020) suggests reviewing each state's rural pandemic readiness plans to identify jurisdictional bounds, designate primary regional hospitals, store medical supplies, and manage health professional shortages.

Health Systems Responsiveness of Respondents. Table 2 indicates health system responsiveness. Respondents always replied to the eight responsiveness domains—respect for dignity, autonomy, privacy and secrecy, timely attention, adequate quality of basic facilities, access to social support, choice of healthcare provider, and effective communication—with a weighted mean of 3.87. Respondents always respect patient rights (WM=3.98).

Table 2. *Health Systems Responsiveness of Respondents*

Health Systems Responsiveness of Respondents	Mean	Verbal Description
Respect for dignity	3.98	Always Responsive
Autonomy (involvement in decisions)	3.98	Always Responsive
Privacy and Confidentiality	3.98	Always Responsive
Prompt Attention	3.78	Always Responsive
Adequate Quality of Basic Amenities	3.82	Always Responsive
Access to social support	3.87	Always Responsive
Choice of health care providers	3.78	Always Responsive
Effective Communication	3.95	Always Responsive
Overall Mean	3.87	Always Responsive

***Legend:** 3.25 – 4.00 Always Responsive (AR)
 2.50 – 3.24 Often Responsive (OR)
 1.75 – 2.49 Sometimes Responsive (SR)
 1.00 – 1.74 Never Responsive (NR)

Health system responsiveness studies involve patients. Patients' healthcare satisfaction varies. This study supports previous findings that respect for human rights area receives the most responsiveness (Baharvand, 2019; Kapologwe et al., 2020; Talasaz et al., 2019; Tille 2019). The health system failed to meet customers' expectations for treatment and convenience, according to Yakob and Ncama (2017). Rapid attention and healthcare provider choice were the lowest. Qin et al. (2022) observed dismal results in both domains, despite rising criteria for safety, quality, and justice.

Correlation of Variables. The profile of the rural health units in terms of the total number of staff does not significantly correlate with the preparedness of the rural health unit as to health facility readiness ($p = 0.247$), health staff members ($p = 0.937$), risk communication ($p = 0.522$) and availability of supplies ($p = 0.924$). This means that the

profile of the RHU had nothing to do with the preparedness. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant relationship was accepted.

Table 2. Correlation Between the Profile of the RHU and Preparedness

		Health Facility Readiness	Health Staff Readiness	Risk Communication	Availability of Supplies
Total No. of Staff	r	-0.129	-0.009	-0.071	-0.011
	p	0.247	0.937	0.522	0.924
Total No. of Covered Barangay	r	0.035	0.061	0.052	0.002
	p	0.755	0.585	0.643	0.986
Average Outpatient Visits Before the Pandemic	r	0.027	0.052	-0.011	-0.007
	p	0.809	0.643	0.922	0.948
Average Outpatient Visits During the Pandemic	r	-0.017	0.02	-0.066	-0.008
	p	0.879	0.857	0.556	0.939

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Since healthcare workers are rare worldwide, the number of providers does not determine disease outbreak readiness. Health workforce training is required now. Nayahangan et al. (2021) advocate immediate IPC and PPE training for healthcare professionals during an outbreak to offer appropriate human resources. COVID-19-trained HCWs felt confidence using PPE to treat suspected or confirmed cases, according to Li et al. (2021). Sultan et al. (2020) found emergency-prepared healthcare staff more confident.

Profile of RHU and Health Systems Responsiveness. The profile of the RHU in terms of the total number of staff was positively correlated with the extent of health systems responsiveness of respondents as to autonomy ($p = 0.018$) and negatively correlated to the choice of health care providers ($p = 0.028$). This result indicates that the higher the number of staff in the RHU, the better the extent of health systems responsiveness of respondents as to autonomy and choice of health care providers. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant relationship was rejected. Research suggests that more healthcare professionals in a facility can increase patient participation and communication, leading to better-quality patient-staff interactions and improved patient satisfaction and safety. Staffing levels are crucial for providing nursing care, monitoring illnesses, and educating patients about self-care. Patients benefit from having more healthcare providers to choose from for continuity of care. Primary care physicians make referrals based on the severity of a patient's ailment, and patients are referred for non-medical reasons such as community standards, patient requests, and education.

RHU Preparedness and Health Systems Responsiveness. The preparedness of rural health units as to health facility readiness was negatively correlated with the extent of health systems responsiveness in terms of prompt attention ($p = 0.003$) and adequate quality of basic amenities ($p = 0.01$). This result means that the lesser the preparedness of the RHU, the better the extent of health systems responsiveness in terms of prompt attention and adequate quality of basic amenities.

Pandemic delay health care and travel because hospitals prepare more. Fear of illness is unreasonable. During enhanced community transmission, Czeisler et al. (2020) found routine and non-emergency care interruptions. Concerned about long hospital waits and doctor-related infections (Devi et al., 2021). They were urged to avoid hospitals unless

Table 3. *Correlation Between the Profile of the RHU and Health Systems*

		Respect for Dignity	Autonomy	Privacy and Confidentiality	Prompt Attention	Adequate Quality of Basic Amenities	Access to Social Support	Choice of Healthcare Providers	Effective Communication
Total No. of Staff	r	0.198	0.258*	0.039	0.052	0.07	0.027	-0.241*	-0.119
	p	0.072	0.018	0.724	0.64	0.529	0.808	0.028	0.286
Total No. of Covered Barangays	r	0.006	0.023	0.028	0.025	0.009	-0.048	0.12	0.006
	p	0.954	0.839	0.802	0.826	0.933	0.667	0.279	0.958
Outpatient Visits Before the Pandemic	r	0.048	0.069	0.141	0.007	-0.029	-0.061	0.103	0.012
	p	0.664	0.538	0.203	0.952	0.798	0.583	0.354	0.914
Outpatient Visits During the Pandemic	r	0.093	0.119	0.155	0.103	0.024	0.048	0.12	0.115
	p	0.405	0.283	0.161	0.355	0.828	0.669	0.281	0.302

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

necessary to reduce transmission risk (Rhatomy & Prasetyo, 2020). These conditions slowed health facility IPC practices.

Pandemic preparation lowers space, ventilation, and seating, despite the IPC interim recommendations to reorganize and improve facility infrastructure. Poor infrastructure, ventilation, airborne infection management, and setting a minimum physical distance have made it difficult for some countries to offer basic services (Garg et al., 2020). WHO IPC requirements require ventilated screening stations, waiting areas, isolation rooms, and patient bathrooms (2021). Outside air ventilation may be impractical. Reducing building or room occupancy can enhance ventilation per person (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2022). Primary care is the health care system's entry point for most people. Minimizing hospital demand and gatekeeping during an outbreak helps vulnerable people cope with their fear of contracting the disease (WHO, 2021).

Conclusions

Primary health care has played a significant role in promoting health and preventing disease transmission. Improving the health system performance by being prepared in times of health crises thus safeguards the welfare of the people.

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: (1) There is a shortage of RHUs and HCWs needed to cater to the city's growing population. During the pandemic, a decline in outpatient visits is noted, which also lessens the delivery and access to healthcare services, (2) Healthcare workers are most at risk of infection, and investing in their health must be taken into consideration to prevent the further shortage of workforce, (3) Although most facilities lack infrastructures, such as dedicated toilets for patient use and single rooms for physical evaluation, Rural Health Units in Cabanatuan City are still better prepared to identify, stop, and prevent epidemics. The sufficient training of HCWs coupled with adequate PPE and IPC supplies are essential factors in delivering safe health services and preventing virus transmission, (4) The health system is always responsive to the non-health needs of the people and has high regard or respect for the patient's human rights, (5) A high quantity of healthcare providers is not required to establish the readiness of a health facility during a disease outbreak since the shortage of healthcare workers has long been experienced in all settings worldwide. However, training is necessary to improve the quality of the health workforce and maintain human resources, (6) Better staffing improves patient interaction and communication, which in turn enables the patient to make informed decisions regarding self-care and enhances patient involvement in their treatment, (7) With fewer health professionals in primary care facilities, especially doctors, patients are given more choices of health providers for referral or continuity of care, and (8) Heightened preparation of health facilities during a pandemic causes less prompt attention due to delays or avoidance in seeking healthcare. It also caused a decrease in adequate quality of basic amenities (e.g., space, ventilation, seating) since facility infrastructure needs restructuring as recommended by the IPC interim guidelines.

Recommendations

The following are suggestions and recommendations developed based on the conclusions drawn: (1) To address the shortage of healthcare workers, the LGU and CHO may invest in protecting their health and well-being by continuous provision and adequate supply of PPE, annual physical examination to monitor their health, mental health breaks (e.g., retreat and recollection), and management of human resources (i.e., recruitment, selection, training, retention), (2) The CHO may conduct the following training and seminars, (3) LGU and CHO may focus on the enhancement of facility infrastructure that may be used with or without an infectious disease outbreak and may boost the IPC in health facilities, (4) To be led by LGU and CHO, social media and technology may be utilized as a platform for health promotion and disease prevention, as well as informing the public about specific disease surveillance. Hotlines that are available 24/7 for emergency concerns, with coordination among LGU and health office and centers, is also suggested, (5) The health workforce is one of the foundations of a responsive health system. Team Building is recommended to develop interpersonal relationships within the organization and create a welcoming environment for the patients, and (6) Research on health systems responsiveness, having patients as respondents, is recommended to evaluate further the responsiveness of health facilities.

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